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ORGANIZATIONAL FORMS OF ADULT EDUCATION IN PENITENTIARY FACILITIES IN THE UK

ABSTRACT

The article justifies the need to develop and improve the system of adult education for convicts scheduled for release. It covers the issues related to the recidivism among convicts. Besides, the article presents a pedagogical analysis of tools of formal, non-formal and informal adult education for convicts in penitentiary facilities in the UK. It specifies organizational conditions of adult education for convicts in penitentiary facilities in this country based on the study of relevant scientific sources and legislative documents. It determines and analyzes organizational forms of adult education for convicts in penitentiary facilities in England and Wales are defined and analyzed. They are the following: the system of obtaining academic qualifications by convicts; the organization of professional training and employment for convicts; correctional programmes for offenders based on the principles of cognitive-behavioural therapy, which aims to change the beliefs and attitudes encouraging criminal behaviour; religious education and upbringing, which promote the rehabilitation of convicts on the personal level; the assistance of penitentiary facilities in establishing social relationships between convicts and their relatives, their positive impact on the reintegration of convicts into society, the motivation of convicts towards learning and acquisition of social skills; "through the gate resettlement programme" based on the establishment of mentorship by probation officers. Finally, the article highlights positive ideas in the UK experience, which can be implemented in the system of convicts' correction and resocialization in Ukraine. Further research should aim to justify forms and methods of non-formal education influencing convicts' resocialization.

Keywords: *rehabilitation of convicts, adult education, organizational forms of education for convicts, forms of education for convicts, penitentiary facilities.*

АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті обґрунтовано нагальність розвитку й удосконалення системи підготовки дорослих засуджених до звільнення. Висвітлено питання, пов'язані з проблемою рецидивної злочинності засуджених до позбавлення волі. Здійснено педагогічний аналіз інструментів формальної, неформальної й інформальної освіти

дорослих засуджених в установах виконання покарань Великої Британії. Проаналізовано організаційні умови освіти дорослих засуджених у пенітенціарних установах країни, що досліджується, на підставі вивчення наукових праць учених й нормативно-правових документів. Визначено й проаналізовано організаційні форми освіти засуджених в установах виконання покарань Англії та Уельсу, а саме: систему отримання академічних кваліфікацій засудженими в умовах позбавлення волі; організацію професійного навчання і зайнятості засуджених; програми корекції поведінки правопорушників, що базуються на принципах когнітивно-поведінкової терапії, яка спрямована на зміну переконань і поглядів, що заохочують злочинну поведінку; релігійне навчання й виховання, яке сприяє реабілітації засудженого на особистісному рівні; сприяння адміністрації виправної установи налагодженню соціальних зв'язків засуджених з рідними, які, окрім свого позитивного впливу на процес реінтеграції у суспільство, мотивують засуджених осіб до більш сумлінного навчання і кращого засвоєння соціальних навичок; програму переселення «Через ворота», в основі якої закладена ідея встановлення менторства над засудженим співробітником органу пробачії. Виокремлено позитивні ідеї досвіду Великої Британії, які потребують подальшого вивчення з метою імплементації їх в систему виправлення і ресоціалізації засуджених в Україні. Зазначено перспективи подальшого дослідження системи освіти засуджених в пенітенціарних установах країни, що досліджується.

Ключові слова: *реабілітація засуджених; освіта засуджених; освіта дорослих; організаційні умови освіти засуджених; форми освіти засуджених; установа виконання покарань.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, one can see how dynamic changes in social, cultural, economic, technological and other spheres in Ukraine state determine qualitative transformations in the adult education system. First of all, there is a transition to lifelong learning. The constant and rapid renewal of knowledge enables the education system to develop and meet the need for continuous acquisition of knowledge and skills in both personal and professional spheres. Lifelong learning combines formal, non-formal and informal education and uses them to stimulate human development, deepen knowledge and enhance the necessary professional skills and self-expression. The challenges Ukraine is facing today require one to develop and implement technologies for adults' personal and professional development, taking into account the needs of marginalized groups to shape and develop social and professional mobility, ensure the competitiveness of youth and adults.

One of the most vulnerable categories of the population in Ukraine is those who are serving or have served their sentences at penitentiary facilities. As of August 30, 2020, there were 51,248 convicts detained in 121 penitentiary facilities under the control of the State Penitentiary Service of Ukraine. It is important to note that 27 penitentiary facilities are in the mode of optimizing their activities; 29 such facilities are located on the territory of the Donetsk and Luhansk Oblasts, which are temporarily not controlled by the Ukrainian authorities; 5 of them – on the temporarily occupied territory of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea (Derzhavna kryminalno-vykonavcha sluzhba Ukrainy, 2020).

According to Art. 1 of the Criminal Executive Code of Ukraine, the Ukrainian criminal executive legislation also aims to create conditions for correction and resocialization of convicts, as well as prevention of new criminal offences by both convicts

and other persons (Kryminalno-vykonavchyy kodeks, 2003). According to Art. 6 of the Criminal Executive Code of Ukraine, the established procedure for serving sentences, probation, community service, social and educational work, general and vocational training are the main tools of correction and resocialization of convicts (Kryminalno-vykonavchyy kodeks, 2003). It is known that three of the six main tools of correction fully, and others only partially, follow the principles, technologies, forms and methods of adult education, penitentiary pedagogy and other related sciences. Therefore, adult education in penitentiary facilities plays an important role in today's development of the penitentiary service and society as a whole. The main objective of adult education in penitentiary facilities is to create the necessary conditions for learning, given the social conditions and demand. Given that the correctional labour code approved on December 23, 1970, expired only in 2004, the main purpose of education in penitentiary facilities up to the early 21st century was to prepare young people for working life. Today, these facilities are designed to provide convicts with comprehensive learning for life in all its manifestations, as well as teach them to adapt to the ongoing changes in the world.

However, several contradictions are making the purpose of the criminal executive legislation somewhat unachievable. Indeed, it is essential to update the content, forms and methods of education for convicts since the existing approaches to their correction and resocialization seem to be rather outdated.

Also, it is vital to study and analyze certain foreign penitentiary systems and implement innovative ideas of their experience in Ukraine. In the UK, adult education for convicts relies on individualization and differentiation of work with different categories of convicts. It is a multidimensional phenomenon which optimally combines the purpose, objectives, content, organizational forms and methods of learning, thus ensuring the integrity and continuity of the training for those scheduled for release. Thus, one should study the UK experience in organizing adult education for convicts to rehabilitate them and ensure the safety of society. It will help Ukrainian practitioners and scholars to update the system of training convicts scheduled for release.

THE AIM OF THE STUDY

The article aims to pedagogically analyze organizational forms of adult education in penitentiary facilities in the UK based on the studies and regulatory documents on the system of rehabilitation for convicts in the mentioned country.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODS

Many Ukrainian scholars have studied organizational forms of education for convicts scheduled for release, as well as other aspects of adult education and socio-educational work in penitentiary facilities (O. Anishchenko, V. Badyra, Ye. Barash, O. Betsa, I. Bohatyrov, V. Chovhan, O. Dzhuzha, O. Duka, A. Halai, O. Kolb, L. Lukianova, V. Pruss, O. Tohochynskyi, O. Tretiak, D. Yahunov et al.). British researchers have devoted their studies to the issues of rehabilitation for convicts and adult education in penitentiary facilities (D. Andrews, A. Bayliss, J. Bonta, J. Braggins, C. Chitty, A. Coyle, E. Hughes, M. Knowles, A. Liebling, J. McGuire, L. Nahmad-Williams, A. Pike, J. Talbot, J. S. Wormith et al.).

The analysis of relevant theses and monographs shows that Ukrainian scholars have not analyzed the issue of education for convicts thoroughly enough yet. Their scientific interests mostly relate to the legal aspects of their formal education. British researchers focus more on the role of education in the process of convicts rehabilitation programmes. For one, A. Pike studies prison-based transformative learning and its role in

life after release, whereas L. Nahmad-Williams considers “the cinderella service’, that is teaching in prisons and young offender institutions in England and Wales.

At the same time, the Ministry of Justice pays significant attention to the education of convicts. At the request of the Ministry, one conducts scientific research on rehabilitation of convicts.

Given that the system of adult education for convicts is viewed as a pedagogical problem, the main research methods include descriptive and systemic-structural ones, which enable theoretical analysis, synthesis, systematization, and generalization of relevant literary sources and foreign experience on the issue in question.

RESULTS

The analysis of authentic materials on the issue in question indicates that the educational process plays a key role in the rehabilitation of convicts in penitentiary facilities in the UK. A review of relevant scientific sources and regulations of the Ministries of Justice of England and Wales concludes that education for convicts is a holistic system which effectively integrates the forms and methods of formal, non-formal and informal adult education sub-systems.

The formulation of the ultimate goal of punishment proves the importance of education in prison. For one, Her Majesty’s Prison and Probation Service documents state that punishment mainly aims to rehabilitate persons in custody or the community by engaging in education and employment (Her Majesty’s Prison & Probation Service, 2019). In May 2016, S. Coates (2016), at the request of the Ministry of Justice, published a document called *Unlocking Potential*, in which she reviewed educational opportunities in prison. The main purpose of this document is “to put the educational process at the centre of the prison regime”. Education is viewed as “one of the pillars of effective rehabilitation” which helps to improve the employment prospects of convicts and their “welfare”, as well as to form “social capital” (Coates, 2016, p. 6). Besides, Coates (2016) encourages one to maintain “a holistic view” on education in prison, which would help convicts to study not only traditional disciplines but also financial literacy, methods of raising children and family relationships (p. 6).

The UK Government subsequently published a White Paper on Prison Security and Reform based on the results of the review. It contains several recommendations, such as to develop a new scheme to train graduates for the monitoring of prisoners “with additional powers to support education at the centre of the prison regime” (Ministry of Justice, 2016b, p. 57). Such training has helped one to inform workers about methodological aspects and organizational conditions of education for convicts in penitentiary facilities. Thus, the UK focuses much on analytical studies on the impact of educational potential on convicts’ resocialization. These studies help one to elaborate on government programmes to improve the organizational framework for convicts’ education and training of relevant personnel.

The findings prove that the UK system of convict rehabilitation programmes offers a wide range of educational services meeting one’s different needs. Such services are available for every convict after an individual plan of their preparation for release with probable risks and needs has been prepared.

The article also describes organizational forms of education for adult convicts in penitentiary facilities in England and Wales. Each of these forms acts as a separate system, implemented by different providers and regulated by relevant regulatory documents of the Ministry of Justice. These include academic qualifications, professional training and

employment, correctional programmes for offenders, religious education and upbringing, social networking, “through the gate resettlement programme”.

Academic qualifications. While in prisons, convicts have the opportunity to obtain academic qualifications, including basic training in English and/or mathematics. This area of work is rather relevant for the UK Government. According to statistics from the Skills Funding Agency, the level of language skills of newly arrived convicts (57 %) barely corresponds to that of 11-year-old children (House of Lords Library Briefing, 2017, p. 6). Moreover, it is much more difficult for an adult with such an educational level to reintegrate into society.

In the UK, the Ministry of Justice provides formal and non-formal education for convicts through two separate areas, namely, the prison education framework and the dynamic purchasing system. Educational services for convicts can also be provided by those who are not members of Her Majesty’s Prison and Probation Service based on contracts with the Department of Business, Innovation and Skills, the Ministry of Justice and the Skills Development Finance Agency. Importantly, convicts may be trained in mathematics, English, English for speakers of other languages, information and communication technologies. It is possible to obtain a qualification from entry-level to a scientific degree through distance learning.

Professional training and employment. Convicts can usually receive vocational training in a certain type of activity while serving their sentences. A study by the Ministry of Justice shows that convicts who received such training in penitentiary facilities are more likely to be employed after release. Thus, vocational training is related to the following areas:

- *catering and hotel business* (such professions as chef, cook, assistant cook, waiter/waitress, bartender, bar supervisor, beverage dispenser, barista, hotel business and catering supervisor);
- construction and planification (such professions as bricklayer, plasterer, joiner, carpenter, construction trade supervisor, artist and decorator, tile fitter, plumber);
- cleaning and maintenance (such professions as cleaning and maintenance worker, operational service worker, waste management worker).

It must be noted that the Department of Business, Innovation and Skills, the Ministry of Justice and the Agency for Financing Skills Development together with employers form the list of professions convicts can obtain in penitentiary facilities based on the labour market analysis. It is not exhaustive and, if possible, the management of penitentiary facilities assists convicts in obtaining professional education and professional qualification under their needs.

Correctional programmes for offenders. These programmes include a series of group therapeutic measures carried out by trained facilitators to reduce the likelihood of re-offending by eliminating the psychological causes of illegal behaviour. The content, forms and methods of this area of work can be attributed to the sub-system of non-formal education for convicts.

The study of relevant documents shows that only programmes which were accredited and proved to be effective can be implemented in penitentiary facilities in the UK. Some programmes aim to reduce the abuse of psychoactive substances since it is because of such substances that former convicts often commit crimes again. The Ministry of Justice has agreed to allocate a special budget for accredited programmes that help offenders to change their behaviour so that such programmes can consider the needs of a particular convict (Ministry of Justice, 2016b, p. 24).

The review of these programmes shows that they follow the principles of cognitive-behavioural therapy which aims to change the beliefs and attitudes encouraging criminal behaviour. They take into account the results of international research which contains evidence in favour of methods of cognitive-behavioural intervention. The latter is proved to be the most effective in correcting illegal behaviour (Ministry of Justice, 2020). In particular, J. McGuire (2008), a professor of forensic clinical psychology at the University of Liverpool, claims that such programmes “usually show a positive effect with a fairly high reliability”. Currently, 24 behavioural programmes are being implemented in penitentiary facilities in the UK. Convicts can also participate in additional 17 accredited programmes after release (Ministry of Justice, 2020).

However, other therapeutic approaches may complement their use in the future. These include psychodrama, virtual reality therapy, emotional intimacy development, art therapy and neurofeedback (House of Lords Library Briefing, 2017, p. 12).

Religious education and upbringing. Prison chaplains provide various religious services in penitentiary facilities in the UK. They act as positive role models and support convicts at particularly difficult times. Importantly, prison chaplains also conduct classes on such issues as loss, empathy for victims, life skills. Some chaplains participate in “family days” during which convicts meet with their partners and family under less restrictive conditions (House of Lords Library Briefing, 2017, p. 15; Ministry of Justice, 2016a).

Some researchers believe that involving convicts in religious traditions helps them to follow the rules of the prison regime. Interestingly, prison chaplains consider rehabilitation to be one of their primary goals. Thus, they promote rehabilitation at the personal level by interacting with prisoners, as well as using both secular and religious counselling methods (Sundt, Dammer, & Cullen, 2002).

Social networking. One of the most important areas in working with convicts is to help them to establish positive relationships with relatives and friends. In addition to their positive impact on reintegration into society, family relationships motivate convicts to study more conscientiously and learn social skills better. Having established positive, professional relationships with convicts’ relatives, the management of penitentiary facilities can influence convicts themselves. This approach is one of the information education technologies (House of Lords Library Briefing, 2017, p. 17).

“Through the Gate Resettlement Programme”. This programme is a form of working with convicts based on the establishment of mentorship by probation officers. They start mentoring convicts from their first day in prison. In particular, probation officers resolve housing and employment issues after convicts’ release and organize their training both in prison and after release. Government reports, however, state that the effectiveness of such rehabilitation is often criticized. Indeed, the impact of mentoring on reducing repeat offences is not significant, given the complexity of controlling convicts after their release and other difficulties that might arise (House of Lords Library Briefing, 2017, p. 21).

In penitentiary facilities in the UK, convicts can also engage in artistic, musical and sporting activities and, thus, reveal and develop their creative and physical potential. There is training in entrepreneurship and self-employment available. It is essential not to neglect the importance of self-education in prison, which is a powerful tool of adult education.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of adult education in penitentiary facilities in the UK shows that education acts as the basis and driving force of convicts’ rehabilitation. The obtained results indicate a wide range of educational services which both convicts and government officials can use to improve the crime situation in the country.

The study of organizational forms of adult education in penitentiary facilities allows one to identify several features which should be further implemented in the Ukrainian system of correction and resocialization. First, the preparation for release is individual. Convicts make an individual plan of their preparation for release with probable risks and needs. Subsequently, it serves as the basis for them to be involved in curricula. Second, also noteworthy is the model of providing all educational services by those who are not members of Her Majesty's Prison and Probation Service. Such services are, in most cases, provided by higher education institutions, governmental organizations responsible for convicts' rehabilitation or non-governmental organizations with the permission and order of the Ministry of Justice. Third, the list of subject areas for courses is periodically updated and accorded with the requirements of the labour market. Convicts are entitled to choose a subject area according to their preferences in any penitentiary facility. Fourth, the forms and methods of behaviour correction programmes follow the principles and techniques of cognitive-behavioural intervention. The sub-system of non-formal education is primarily aimed at eliminating such criminogenic factors as the use of psychoactive substances and establishing positive relationships with others. Indeed, without solving these problems, convicts will find it impossible to live in the community after their release. Besides, one should pay particular attention to the financing of correctional programmes from a special budget. It allows penitentiary facilities to freely choose the methods of working with convicts.

Thus, the article proves that non-formal education of convicts implemented in penitentiary facilities through behaviour correction programmes can activate internal resources for resocialization and actions for the benefit of the community. It is non-formal education that enables convicts to learn, shape their position on the surrounding reality and participate in various forms of prosocial activities.

Further research should aim to justify forms and methods of non-formal education influencing convicts' resocialization. After all, it is vital to update the methods of working with convicts based on the principles of non-formal education.

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